

Kinetics of Oxidative Decarboxylation of Amino Acids by Bromamine-T in Alkaline Medium

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Kinetics of oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by bromamine-T has been studied in alkaline medium at 293 K. The rate followed first order kinetics in [oxidant], zero order in [amino acid] and fractional order in [OH⁻]. The rate increased with an increase in ionic strength of the medium. Addition of the reduced product of oxidant (*p*-toluenesulphonamide) decreased the rate. The rate increased with a decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. The activation parameters have also been computed. The oxidation process has been shown to proceed via two paths. The mechanisms proposed and the deduced rate laws are in conformity with the observed kinetics. The coefficients of the rate-controlling steps have also been computed.

AMINO acid reactions have drawn the attention of many investigators due to their biological activity.

In continuation of our earlier work¹⁻⁵ on the kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by chloramine-T¹⁻⁴ and bromamine-T⁵ in acid and alkaline media, we report herein the kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by bromamine-T in alkaline medium. The present investigation was necessitated to compare the kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by structurally related reagents under identical reaction conditions.

Experimental

Bromamine-T (BAT) was prepared by the partial debromination of dibromamine-T and its aqueous solution was standardised iodometrically and stored in dark coloured bottles. Chromatographically pure L-glycine (Gly), L-alanine (Ala), L-valine (Val), L-leucine (Leu), L-serine (Ser), L-arginine (Arg) and L-glutamine (Gln) (Sisco, India) were further assayed and their aqueous stock solutions were prepared. All other reagents employed were of AnalaR grade. Ionic strength of the reaction medium was kept high (0.3 mol dm⁻³) by using a concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic investigations were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions with [amino acid] always greater than [BAT]. The required amounts of amino acid solution (0.5–5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³), NaOH (0.02–0.2 mol dm⁻³), sodium perchlorate (0.3 mol dm⁻³) and water (to keep total volume constant) in the glass-stoppered boiling tube were thermally equilibrated at the desired temperature. The reaction was initiated by the rapid addition of a known quantity of BAT solution (1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric

estimation of unreacted BAT at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) computed from the plots of log [BAT]₀ vs time were reproducible within ± 4%.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the oxidations was determined by thermally equilibrating varying ratios of [BAT] to [amino acid] for 24 h always under [amino acid] >> [BAT] condition at different [OH⁻] (0.02–0.2 mol dm⁻³). The products NH₃, CO₂, *p*-toluenesulphonamide (PTS) and the respective aldehyde were identified^{6,7}, and the aldehydes were quantitatively estimated⁸. The observed stoichiometry may be represented as

where, R = CH₂C₆H₄SO₂; R' = H (Gly), CH₃ (Ala), (CH₃)₂CH (Val), (CH₃)₂CHCH₂ (Leu), HOCH₂ (Ser), H₂NC(NH)NH(CH₂)₃ (Arg) and H₂NCOCH₂-CH₂ (Gln).

Results

The kinetics of oxidations were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants in alkaline media (0.02–0.2 mol dm⁻³). The results are presented in Tables 1–3. At constant [NaOH] with several fold excess of amino acid, plots of log [BAT]₀/[BAT] vs time were linear upto 75% of the reaction. At constant [BAT] and [amino acid], the rate increased with increase in [NaOH] with all the amino acids. pH values of the reaction mixtures were measured as [NaOH] was varied and the true [OH⁻] in the reaction mixtures were calculated (Table 4). The plots of log *k*_{obs} vs log [OH⁻] were linear with all the amino acids with fractional slopes.

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} against $[OH^-]$; (●) Gly, (x) Ala, (◆) Val, (⊕) Leu, (■) Ser, (□) Arg, and (○) Gln, $10^2[BAT]=10^2[A.A]=20$ [NaOH]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, $\mu=0.3$ mol dm⁻³, Temp.=293 K.

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[OH^-]$ were also linear with finite intercepts in all cases (Fig. 1) indicating two-pathway mechanism for the oxidation. The rate was independent of [amino acid] with all the amino acids (Table 1). The rates increased with increase in ionic strength of the medium (0.1–0.5 mol dm⁻³) (Table 2). Addition of PTS, the reduced product of oxidant, decreased the rate in all cases. But a decrease in dielectric constant of the

medium by changing the solvent composition with methanol increased the rate with all the amino acids. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ were linear with positive slopes.

The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters were computed from the Arrhenius plots with all the amino acids (Table 3)

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS AND OH⁻ CONCENTRATION ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION
Temp.=293 K, $\mu=0.3$ mol dm⁻³

[A.A] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[BAT] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[NaOH] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$						
			Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser	Arg	Gln
1.0	1.0	2.0	5.83	10.3	2.26	5.3	11.0	13.4	4.8
1.0	1.0	4.0	—	—	—	—	24.1	—	10.3
1.0	1.0	5.0	20.6	34.3	3.29	10.5	36.6	22.2	12.1
1.0	1.0	7.5	—	52.8	—	13.3	54.4	26.3	18.5
1.0	1.0	10.0	42.6	65.7	4.44	15.7	67.2	29.8	22.7
1.0	1.0	15.0	61.9	—	5.02	—	—	—	—
1.0	1.0	20.0	83.2	143.5	5.46	21.3	110.3	40.9	47.8
1.0	0.5	5.0	20.1	34.2	3.12	10.3	36.8	22.2	12.3
1.0	0.75	5.0	20.7	33.4	3.35	10.6	36.7	21.9	12.2
1.0	1.0	5.0	20.6	34.3	3.29	10.5	36.6	22.2	12.1
1.0	2.0	5.0	19.4	35.1	3.05	10.5	36.8	22.3	11.9
0.5	1.0	5.0	20.7	34.2	3.17	10.5	36.9	22.2	12.8
0.75	1.0	5.0	18.6	34.3	3.21	10.3	36.7	22.3	11.8
1.0	1.0	5.0	20.6	34.3	3.29	10.5	36.6	22.2	12.1
2.0	1.0	5.0	20.8	34.2	3.34	10.2	36.8	21.5	12.1
5.0	1.0	5.0	20.6	34.4	3.38	10.4	36.2	22.1	12.2

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF *p*-TOLUENESULPHONAMIDE (PTS), IONIC STRENGTH AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF REACTION MEDIUM ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

Temp., = 293 K [PTS] $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$						
	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser	Arg	Gln
0	20.6	34.3	3.89	10.5	36.6	22.2	12.1
2.0	14.4	27.2	2.14	7.0	17.3	17.2	8.2
4.0	8.8	19.0	1.51	6.0	10.9	11.6	4.6
5.0	6.9	16.2	1.35	5.6	9.6	9.9	3.8
μ							
0.1	18.9	31.5	3.05	10.2	34.3	19.8	10.8
0.2	19.7	32.1	3.15	10.3	35.1	20.6	11.2
0.3	20.6	34.3	3.89	10.5	36.6	22.2	12.1
0.5	24.2	37.5	4.28	11.4	40.6	26.9	13.1
<i>D</i>							
80.2	20.6	34.3	3.89	10.5	36.6	22.2	12.1
75.5	26.9	46.1	4.63	11.5	50.7	24.2	17.5
70.9	32.6	56.3	6.02	15.4	71.2	28.7	26.1
66.2	37.6	—	8.60	19.7	—	35.0	35.7

$10^3[\text{BAT}] = 10^3[\text{AA}] = 20[\text{NaOH}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY BAT

	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser	Arg	Gln
$\log A$	11.2	14.8	21.3	18.4	14.6	14.6	13.5
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	55.7	74.5	116.4	98.0	73.4	74.7	69.7
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	50.6	71.0	114.3	94.6	71.4	73.0	68.0
$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-123.9	-49.6	78.1	19.9	-48.8	-46.9	-68.7
$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	86.9	85.5	91.5	88.8	85.7	86.7	88.1

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF pH OF REACTION MIXTURES WITH [NaOH]

[NaOH] $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	pH						
	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser	Arg	Gln
2.0	11.78	11.68	11.71	11.69	11.72	11.51	11.77
5.0	12.42	12.38	12.41	12.40	12.44	12.42	12.45
7.5	—	12.57	—	—	12.64	—	12.65
10.0	12.74	12.69	12.71	12.75	12.78	12.67	12.79
15.0	12.90	—	—	—	—	—	—
20.0	13.16	13.16	12.97	13.25	12.98	12.93	13.03

Discussion

The dissociation of amino acid is pH-dependent. In strongly acidic solutions, it exists in the cationic form $\text{R}'\text{CH}(\text{NH}_3^+)\text{COOH}$ which changes over to zwitter ionic form $\text{R}'\text{CH}(\text{NH}_3^+)\text{COO}^-$ and finally to anionic form $\text{R}'\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COO}^-$ in strongly alkaline solutions.

Bromamine-T, analogous to bromamine-B⁹, is a fairly strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions^{1,10} and dissociates of RNBr^- and Na^+ . The conjugate acid (RNHBr) formed in the presence of H^+ ions undergoes disproportionation to dibromamine-T ($2\text{RNHBr} \rightleftharpoons \text{RNH}_2 + \text{RNBr}_2$) and hydrolyses to hypobromous acid ($\text{RNHBr} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{RNH}_2 + \text{HOBr}$). HOBr in turn gives hypobromite ($\text{HOBr} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{OBr}^-$, $K_a = 2.0 \times 10^{-9}$ at 25°) in the alkaline medium.

Hence, the probable oxidising species in alkaline solutions of BAT^1 , depending upon the pH of the medium, are RNBr^- , RNHBr , HOBr and OBr^- .

Mechanism of oxidation: The kinetics of first order in $[\text{BAT}]$, zero order in [amino acid] and fractional order in $[\text{OH}^-]$ observed with all the amino acids may be explained by two-pathway mechanism as the oxidant (RNHBr) can undergo disproportionation in two competitive steps.

The corresponding rate law (2) is

$$-d[BAT]/dt = k_1[BAT][H_2O] \quad (2)$$

$$k_{obs} = -d \ln [BAT]/dt = k_1[H_2O] \quad (3)$$

The related rate law is

$$-d[BAT]/dt = k_6[BAT][OH^-] \quad (4)$$

or $k_{obs} = k_6[OH^-] \quad (5)$

The combined rate law,

$$k_{obs} = k_1[H_2O] + k_6[OH^-] \quad (6)$$

accounts for the observed kinetics. Further, the linearity between k_{obs} and $[OH^-]$ with finite inter-

cepts supports the rate law (6) (Fig. 1). The constants k_1 and k_6 were computed in all cases from the slopes and intercepts of the plots, k_{obs} vs $[OH^-]$ and with $[H_2O] = 55.56 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 5).

Increase of rate with increase in ionic strength of the medium and negative values for the entropy of activation support the participation of like ions in the rate determining steps. Free energy of activation is almost constant in all cases; and a plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ was linear with an isokinetic temperature of about 318.7 K showing the operation of similar mechanism in the oxidation of all the amino acids.

Comparison of present kinetic data for the oxidation of amino acids by BAT in alkaline medium with those for oxidations with CAT (Table 6), a structurally similar reagent, reveals that BAT is a more powerful oxidant than CAT. In other words, BAT donates Br^+ species much more readily than CAT does Cl^+ species.

Many theories¹¹⁻¹³ have been put forward to give a quantitative explanation for the effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the kinetics of liquid phase reactions. The observed increase of rate with a decrease in D is in conformity with the Laidler and Eyring equation¹¹ (7),

$$\ln k = \ln k_0 + \frac{Nz^2e^2}{2DRT}(1/r - 1/r_\ddagger) \quad (7)$$

where, k_0 is the rate constant in a medium of infinite dielectric constant and r and $r_\ddagger$ refer to radii of the reactant species and activated complex. It is evident from equation (7) that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant when $r_\ddagger > r$. In the present investigation, it is likely that $r_\ddagger > r$ as the reaction may involve like ions in the rate determining steps.

TABLE 5

	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser	Arg	Gln
$10^3 k_6$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	7.47	12.2	0.44	2.21	10.9	3.93	3.93
$10^3 k_1$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	4.50	9.0	3.60	7.65	11.7	23.4	2.70

TABLE 6—COMPARISON OF KINETIC DATA FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY CAT AND BAT IN ALKALINE MEDIUM

Amino acids	CAT Order with respect to			BAT Order with respect to		
	[CAT]	[Amino acid]	$[OH^-]$	[BAT]	[Amino acid]	$[OH^-]$
Gly	1	1	-0.90	1	0	0.90
Ala	1	1	-0.83	1	0	0.89
Val	1	1	-0.81	1	0	0.82
Leu	1	1	-0.98	1	0	0.40
Ser	1	1	-0.96	1	0	0.76
Arg	1	1	-0.79	1	0	0.33
Gln	—	—	—	1	0	0.67

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